

UNDERSTANDING DEEPANA PACHANA IN THE LIGHT OF GUNA SIDHANTHA AND ITS ROLE IN GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDERS***¹Dr. Sivaprasadan V., ²Dr. Shylamma TM, ³Dr. Sunil John Thykkattil, ⁴Dr Sethu Raj K S**¹PG. Scholar Department of Kayachikitsa, Govt. Ayurveda Medical College, Tripunithura.²Professor and HOD, Department of Kayachikitsa, Government Ayurveda College, Thripunithura, Ernakulam.³Associate Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa, Government Ayurveda College, Thripunithura, Ernakulam.⁴Asso Prof Department of Samhitha Samskritha Evum Sidhantha, Govt Ayurveda College Tripunithura, Ernakulam.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Sivaprasadan V.**

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ABSTRACT

Guna siddhanta forms the fundamental cornerstone of ayurvedic pharmacology, offering profound insights into the therapeutic potential and mode of action of various substances^[1] Its relevance is significant in many disorders, where maintaining the functional integrity of agni is central to health.^[2] According to ayurveda, impaired digestion leads to the formation of ama, which in turn initiates a cascade of pathological processes.^[3] In this context, deepana (stimulation of agni) and pachana dravyas are indispensable tools, classified and understood on the basis of their inherent gunas^[4] (qualities). Among these, katu pachana is primarily defined by its ushna veerya, laghu, and ruksha gunas.^[5] These attributes create an optimal internal environment for agni to function effectively, thereby ensuring the proper breakdown of food and elimination of ama.^[6] Classical examples include ginger and black pepper, which demonstrate both deepana and pachana effects, simultaneously enhancing digestive capacity and resolving metabolic toxins.^[7] Such herbs are particularly beneficial in conditions involving kapha and vata imbalance.^[8s] where sluggish digestion and ama accumulation are predominant. In contrast, thiktha pachana is characterized by seetha veerya, laghu, and ruksha gunas.^[9] Unlike katu dravyas, these agents focus more on the digestion and elimination of ama without directly stimulating agni.^[10] This makes them particularly suitable in conditions where pitta aggravation is a concern, as they clear toxins gently while preventing excessive stimulation of digestive fire.^[11] A classical formulation representing this group is shadanga panam, which is frequently employed in fevers and digestive disorders associated with toxin accumulation.^[12] By integrating ayurvedic principles with modern clinical understanding, the application of guna siddhanta in the choice between katu and thiktha pachana can provide highly individualized therapeutic outcomes.^[13] Gastrointestinal conditions such as irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), indigestion, hyperacidity, gastroesophageal reflux disease^[14] (GERD) etc highlight the need for precision in drug selection, wherein the practitioner tailors therapy based on constitution (prakriti), doshic imbalance, and disease stage. Thus, understanding the nuanced differences between katu and thiktha pachana in the light of guna siddhanta not only enriches ayurvedic therapeutics but also establishes a rational and scientific approach to managing gastrointestinal disorders.^[15]

KEYWORDS: *Guna sidhantha, katu pachana, thiktha pachana, nijavikara, Sudha chikitsa, asudhachikitsa etc.***INTRODUCTION**

In Ayurveda, the concept of agni is considered the very foundation of health and well-being.^[16] All processes of digestion, metabolism, and transformation in the body are governed by agni.^[17] When agni functions properly, food is digested well, tissues are nourished, and strength is maintained.^[18] But when agni becomes weak or

disturbed, ama is formed.^[19] This ama obstructs the channels of the body (srotas), leading to many gastrointestinal as well as systemic disorders.^[20] Thus, the first line of management in Ayurveda is always directed toward restoring the balance of agni and removing ama.

deepana dravyas alone will not work because stimulating an already active agni may cause athygni may lead to complication. Conversely, if agni is weak without the presence of ama, deepana dravyas are prescribed to rekindle digestive fire. When both ama and poor agni coexist, medicines possessing both deepana–pachana properties should be used.

Katu pachana dravyas, owing to their ushna veerya, are suitable in kapha-vata conditions like indigestion and IBS, where agni requires stimulation. However, their indiscriminate use in pitta-dominant disorders can worsen symptoms may cause inflammation. On the other hand, tikta pachana dravyas, with sheeta veerya, gently digest ama and simultaneously pacify aggravated pitta.^[20] Classical formulations such as guloochyadi kashayam, drakshaadi kashaya etc exemplify all this approach, being particularly effective in vidagdha pitta, paithika jwara, and raktatisara.

The clinical application of these principles highlights the precision of Ayurvedic pharmacology. Thus, the differentiation between *deepana* and *pachana* based on *guna* is not merely theoretical but highly practical. It prevents improper drug selection, ensures targeted therapy, and restores digestive balance without causing adverse effects. The study underscores that treatment guided by *guna siddhanta* enhances therapeutic outcomes and exemplifies the personalized approach of Ayurveda.

CONCLUSION

In ayurveda, the distinction between *sudha Chikitsa* and *asudha chikitsa* is of great importance.^[21,22,23] A common misconception is that ayurvedic medicines never cause adverse reactions. However, if treatment is not guided by the principles of *guna siddhanta* and proper drug selection, it may result in complications and even fatal outcomes. The scientific framework of *guna siddhanta* helps in selecting appropriate *deepana* and *pachana* therapies based on the doshic imbalance. For instance, *katu pachana* is indicated in *kapha-vata* conditions with impaired agni, whereas *tikta pachana* is more suitable in *pitta-related* disorders. Failure to apply these principles correctly may lead to adverse effects, such as slow damage to vital organs like liver or persistent irritation that, over time, could predispose to carcinogenic changes. Thus, Ayurveda strongly emphasizes *Sudha Chikitsa*, ensuring safe, effective, minimise complication and scientifically justified treatment.^[10]

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